

Abstract and Bibliographic Information for Periodicity of Strength of Pattern in Binocular Rivalry (1986)

Originally published as:

Sohmiya, T. & Sohmiya, K. Periodicity of Strength of Pattern in Binocular Rivalry. *Perceptual and Motor Skills*, 1986, 62(3), 943-950.

DOI: [10.2466/pms.1986.62.3.943](https://doi.org/10.2466/pms.1986.62.3.943)

Abstract

The effect of suppression in binocular rivalry is divided into the effects of boundary and of region. By removing the effect of boundary from the double effects, we examined whether the strength of pattern oscillates throughout the duration of the suppression phase. Probabilities of appearance of the suppressed test patterns were measured immediately after the removal of the suppressing pattern at various temporal points after the onset of suppression. The probabilities decrease, reach a minimum level, and then increase throughout the course of the suppression phase. Immediately after the beginning of the suppression phase, the small test pattern whose duration of suppression is short rarely appears, while the large pattern whose duration of suppression is long certainly appears. These results support our hypothesis for which the key assumption is that the strength of pattern periodically oscillates as a function of duration of observation time.

About Terminology

When publishing these findings in an international journal ten years after the original 1976 works, several technical terms were revised as follows:

Intermittent Figure (IF) → Suppressing Pattern (SP)

Figure Strength → Strength of Pattern

Figure Strength of IF → Effect of Boundary

Peripheral Light → Effect of Region

The rationale behind these terminological revisions will be explained in future publications. For the time being, readers may understand the relationships among these terms as follows:

Suppressing Pattern (SP) = Intermittent Figure (IF)

Strength of Pattern = Figure Strength

Effect of Boundary approximately corresponds to what was termed “Figure Strength of IF” in the 1976 works.

Effect of Region approximately corresponds to what was termed “Peripheral Light” in the 1976 works.

Differences Between the 1976 Works and the 1986 Paper

In 1976, Sohmiya Tamotsu gave a solo oral presentation at the 40th Annual Convention of the Japanese Psychological Association (Chukyo University, September 29). On the same day, the co-authored book “Fundamental Study on Pattern Recognition by a New Experimental Method” (Tamotsu Sohmiya & Kazuko Sohmiya, Maruzen) went on sale.

In these works, the following seven conceptual components were presented:

1. The flickering method.

2. The definition of figure strength.
3. Analyses of figure strength and peripheral light including their relationships to luminance, reflectance, and illuminance. (Presented exclusively in Chapters 2 and 3 of the 1976 book.)
4. Findings demonstrating that experimental data obtained via the flickering method are well accounted for by the hypothesis that figure strength oscillates periodically.
5. The verification experiments for the aforementioned oscillatory hypothesis.
6. The proposal of the Synchronous Oscillation Hypothesis, which posits that perceptual grouping and other Gestalt characteristics can be explained by the phase synchronization of these periodic oscillations.
7. A theoretical proposal extending this hypothesis to explain the mechanisms of consciousness and self-identity. (Appeared only in the 1976 conference presentation.)

Component 3 was unique to the book, and content 7 was unique to the conference presentation. All other points were common to both 1976 works. The 1986 paper reports only components 1 through 5 in English. In other words, the Synchronous Oscillation Hypothesis (component 6) and the theoretical proposals regarding consciousness and self-identity (component 7) were intentionally excluded from the 1986 paper.

The experimental data presented in the 1986 paper represent an English-language republication of the experiments already conducted and reported in 1976.

Reason for Exclusion

According to a primary document written by Sohmiya Tamotsu (The Final Research History of Tamotsu Sohmiya and Kazuko Sohmiya) and oral testimony conveyed on multiple occasions to Seiyu Sohmiya, manuscripts concerning the Synchronous Oscillation Hypothesis faced consecutive rejections by Japanese academic journals.

As a strategic decision aimed at facilitating publication in an overseas peer-reviewed journal, the authors chose to omit theoretical claims associated with the Synchronous Oscillation Hypothesis.

External Links

Semantic Scholar (Figures and Table):

[View Link](<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Periodicity-of-Strength-of-Pattern-in-Binocular-Sohmiya-Sohmiya/90a3bad97d62ad0be743b4d2128609197e28c65a>)

Related

・ 新実験法によるパターン認識の基礎的研究 / Fundamental Study on Pattern Recognition by a New Experimental Method
<https://zenodo.org/records/20565921>

・ A Unified Explanation of the Gestalt Laws by Synchronous Oscillations of Figure Strength
(English Translation of the 1976 Conference Paper)
<https://zenodo.org/records/20533060>

Document Metadata

This description and record were prepared by Seiyu Sohmiya, a research collaborator during the original study and the son of the authors.

Unless otherwise noted, statements concerning the historical background, terminology, publication history, and editorial decisions described in this record are based on archival materials preserved by the Sohmiya family, including written records by Tamotsu Sohmiya and Kazuko Sohmiya, unpublished research materials, and oral testimony communicated to Seiyu Sohmiya.